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Value of $\sqrt{2}$ according to Śulvasūtra and Modern Calculation

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The Vedas are the oldest Indo-European literary monuments, reflecting the socio-cultural status of the ancient Indian people. The Rigveda is the oldest Veda, in which the very first mantra says - “अग्निमिते पुरोहितं यज्ञस्य देवमृत्विजम् । होतारं रत्नधातमम्”¹. This mantra is clearly mentioned the words ‘Yajña’, ‘Purohita’, ‘Rtvija’ and ‘Hotā’. The Yajña is to be performed in the guidance of Purohita - Rtvija - Hotā, hence it is clear that that Yajña is as old as the Veda. Brāhmaṇ literature described ‘Yajña Karma’ is the best deed in humans’ lives, it is a complete way of life.² The Vedāṅga literature was developed to properly understand all the applications, especially the sacrificial implementation of the Veda. Śulvasūtra is a part of the Kalpa Vedāṅga, developed in 800 BC.

The Śulvasūtra deals with the rules of the proper construction of sacrificial altars as par the requirement of the sacrifices, which shapes are like square, triangle, trapezium, circle, Pentagonal, Hexagonal, Heptagonal and many others. Consequently, the Śulvasūtras got involved in Mathematical

¹ Rgveda 1.1.1

² Śatpatha Brāhmaṇ. 1.7.1.2 “यज्ञो वै श्रेष्ठतमं कर्म”; Taittiriya Brāhmaṇ. 3.2.1.4 “यज्ञो हि श्रेष्ठतमं कर्म”

calculations and Geometric speculations. In the *Śulvasūtras*, a surd is technically called *karaṇī*. Like- *dvi-karaṇī* means $\sqrt{2}$, *tri-karaṇī* = $\sqrt{3}$, *trīya-karaṇī* = $\sqrt{\frac{1}{3}}$, *aṣṭādaśa-karaṇī* = $\sqrt{18}$ etc.

Boudhāyana, *Āpastamba* and *Kātyāyana* have given the value of $\sqrt{2}$ in their *Śulvasūtras* with a particular term ‘*viśeṣa*.’³ *Boudhāyana* and *Āpastamba* say – ‘प्रमाणं तृतीयेन वर्धयेत्तच्च चतुर्थेनात्मचतुस्त्रिंशोनेन, सविशेषः’⁴ - means the measure (of which the *dvi-karaṇī* is to be found) is to be increased by its third part and this (third part) again by the fourth part less by the thirty-fourth part (of this fourth part). This is (the value thus obtained is called) the *saviśeṣa*. *Kātyāyana* defines the rule in nearly similar words. करणीं तृतीयेन वर्धयेत्तच्च स्वचतुर्थेनात्मचतुस्त्रिंशोनेन स विशेष इति विशेषः⁵ means is to be increased by its third and this (third) again by its own fourth less the thirty-fourth part (of that fourth); this is the (the value of) diagonal of a square (whose side is the measure); this is approximate.

Thus, if x be the *dvi-karaṇī* of y, that is, if x be the side of a square whose area is double that of the square on y, then according to the rule

$$x = y + \frac{y}{3} + \frac{y}{3 \times 4} - \frac{y}{3 \times 4 \times 34}$$

Now, it has been stated before, the diagonal of a square is its *dvi-karaṇī*. So, this rule gives the relation between the diagonal and said of a square. Indeed, the above the law is mainly meant to define that relationship. Thus, we get

$$\sqrt{2} = 1 + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{3 \times 4} - \frac{1}{3 \times 4 \times 34}$$

Example:

ABC is a circle such that AC = CB

³ *viśeṣa* refers to a small quantity, which is either in excess or in deficit, and cannot be accurately determined.

⁴ BŚS-1.61-62, ĀŚS-1.12

⁵ KŚS-2.13

$$= 1 \text{ and } AB = \sqrt{2}, \angle ACB = 90^\circ$$

$$OB = OC = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}$$

Taking B as center and BC as radius draw an arc which cuts AB at D

$$BD = BC = 1$$

$$OD = 1 - \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} = \frac{\sqrt{2}-1}{\sqrt{2}}$$

$$\therefore AD = \sqrt{2} - 1$$

In triangle DOC, $CD^2 = DO^2 + OC^2$

$$= \left(1 - \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\right)^2 = \left(\frac{\sqrt{2}-1}{\sqrt{2}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\right)^2$$

$$\therefore DC^2 = \frac{1}{2} (2 - 2\sqrt{2} + 1) + \frac{1}{2} = 2 - \sqrt{2}$$

$$\therefore DC = \sqrt{2 - \sqrt{2}}$$

Drop $DG \perp r$ to AC.

$$DG^2 = AD^2 - AG^2 = CD^2 - CG^2, CG = AC - AG$$

$$\therefore AD^2 - AG^2 = CD^2 - (AC - AG)^2 = CD^2 - AC^2 + 2AC \cdot AG - AG^2$$

$$\therefore AG = \frac{AD^2 - CD^2 + AC^2}{2AB} = \frac{(\sqrt{2}-1)^2 - (2-\sqrt{2}) + 1^2}{2 \times 1} = \frac{2-\sqrt{2}}{2}$$

$$DG^2 = AD^2 - AG^2 = (\sqrt{2} - 1)^2 - \left(\frac{2-\sqrt{2}}{2}\right)^2 = 1\frac{1}{2} - \sqrt{2}$$

$$\therefore DG = \sqrt{\frac{3}{2} - \sqrt{2}} = 1 - \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}$$

Taking D as center and DG as radius draw an arc which cuts AC at H.

$$\therefore DH = DG$$

Drop $HI \perp r$ to AG

$$\begin{aligned} AH &= AB - BD - DH \\ &= \sqrt{2} - 1 - \left(1 - \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\right) \\ &= \frac{3-2\sqrt{2}}{\sqrt{2}} \end{aligned}$$

ΔAHI and ΔADG are similar

$$\therefore \frac{AH}{AD} = \frac{HI}{DG} \quad \therefore HI = \frac{AH}{AD} \cdot DG$$

$$\begin{aligned} HI &= \frac{(3-2\sqrt{2})}{(\sqrt{2}-1) \times (\sqrt{2})} \times \left(1 - \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\right) \\ &= \frac{5\sqrt{2}-7}{2(\sqrt{2}-1)} \end{aligned}$$

$$HI = HJ = \frac{5\sqrt{2}-7}{2(\sqrt{2}-1)}$$

Drop $JK \perp r$ to AI

ΔAJK and ΔAHI are similar

$$\therefore \frac{AJ}{AH} = \frac{JK}{HI} \quad \therefore JK = \frac{AJ}{AH} \cdot HI$$

$$\begin{aligned} AJ &= AB - BD - DH - HJ \\ &= \sqrt{2} - 1 - \left(1 - \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\right) - \left(\frac{5\sqrt{2}-7}{2(\sqrt{2}-1)}\right) \\ &= \frac{17\sqrt{2}-24}{2\sqrt{2}(\sqrt{2}-1)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \therefore JK &= \left\{ \frac{\frac{17\sqrt{2}-24}{2\sqrt{2}(\sqrt{2}-1)}}{\frac{3-2\sqrt{2}}{\sqrt{2}}} \times \frac{\frac{5\sqrt{2}-7}{2(\sqrt{2}-1)}}{1} \right\} \\ &= \frac{17\sqrt{2}-24}{2\sqrt{2}(\sqrt{2}-1)} \times \frac{5\sqrt{2}-7}{2(\sqrt{2}-1)} \times \frac{\sqrt{2}}{3-2\sqrt{2}} \\ &= \frac{338-239\sqrt{2}}{68-48\sqrt{2}} \end{aligned}$$

$$AB = BD + DH + HJ + JK$$

$$\therefore \sqrt{2} = 1 + 1 - \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} + \frac{5\sqrt{2}-7}{2(\sqrt{2}-1)} + \frac{338-239\sqrt{2}}{68-48\sqrt{2}}$$

$$\sqrt{2} = \frac{5572}{3940} = \frac{1393}{985}$$

$$= 1 + \frac{408}{985} = 1 + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{239}{2955} = 1 + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{3 \times 4} - \frac{87}{2955 \times 12}$$

$$\text{Now } 87 \times 34 = 2958 = 2955$$

$$= 1 + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{3 \times 4} - \frac{87}{3 \times 4 \times 87 \times 34}$$

$$\therefore \sqrt{2} = 1 + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{3 \times 4} - \frac{1}{3 \times 4 \times 34}$$

In decimal fraction, the value of $\sqrt{2} = 1.4142156863\dots$

According to modern calculation $\sqrt{2} = 1.41421356\dots$

Thus, the value of $\sqrt{2}$ as obtained by the ancient Hindus is correct up to 5 places of decimals. The commentator *Rāma* was an inhabitant of *Naimiṣa* (near modern Lucknow, India). He has written the commentaries on the *Kātyāyana Śulvasūtra* and *Śāradā-tilaka-Tantra*. His book *Kuṇḍākṛti* was composed in *Vikrama saṁvāt* 1506 (1449 A.D.). The most notable contribution of his is a correction to the well-known *Śulvasūtra* value of $\sqrt{2}$ namely-

$$\sqrt{2} = 1 + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{3 \times 4} - \frac{1}{3 \times 4 \times 34}$$

Rāma shows that a more accurate (*Sūkṣmatara*) value of $\sqrt{2}$

$$\left[\sqrt{2} = 1 + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{3 \times 4} - \frac{1}{3 \times 4 \times 34} - \frac{1}{3 \times 4 \times 34 \times 33} + \frac{1}{3 \times 4 \times 34 \times 34} \right]$$

Turned into decimal fraction the expression gives

$$\sqrt{2} = 1.4142156863\dots \quad \text{(i) As per Śulvasūtra}$$

$$\sqrt{2} = 1.414213502\dots \quad \text{(ii) As per Rāma}$$

$$\sqrt{2} = 1.41421356\dots\dots \quad \text{(iii) As per modern calculations.}$$

Thus, that value which is given by *Rāma* is correct up to seven places of decimals and that of *Śulvasūtras* up to five places of decimals. So, it is clear that the *Śulvasūtras* attained, a very remarkable degree of accuracy in calculating an approximate value of $\sqrt{2}$.

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